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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Debris disks represent the longest lived example of circumstellar disks, generated by collisions of planetesimals before, throughout and beyond the main sequence lifetime of a star. Such disks are typically faint and most were detected via infrared or submm excess above the expected photospheric emission.

Looking forward, the most fundamental progress on debris disks requires large single dish capabilities in the mid-IR, the far-IR and the submm/mm. A strong concept in the submm is the Atacama Large Aperture Submillimetre Telescope (AtLAST), which will be able to detect statistically significant numbers of new disks (1000s rather than 100s), including those around M-stars, to a fractional luminosity level at or below that of the Kuiper belt. Such a telescope would have 2" resolution at 350 μ m, meaning that belts comparable scale to the Edgeworth-Kuiper Belt would be resolvable to a distance of 30-40 pc. AtLAST would be a particularly compatible facility with ALMA, which, although powerful, is not an optimal facility for imaging of nearby debris disks since even in its lowest resolution configuration, large scale emission is filtered out. A facility like AtLAST would also have access to the molecular spectra from these 1000s of detected disks to characterize the kinematics via gas emission.

Emission from the cold dust components of debris disks peaks in the far-infrared. SPICA will have some capability at this wavelength, but its size limits debris disk imaging to only the nearest disks, and its sensitivity will be severely hindered by confusion with the extragalactic background. The far-IR facility that best meets our requirements is the Origins Space Telescope. At 9m in diameter, the full scope mission would provide images at 100 μ m imaging at the 2" scale, comparable to AtLAST.

In the mid-infrared, SPICA also has some capability, particularly with respect to spectroscopy, which will be excellent for the detection of solid state features and detection of atomic and molecular species in the gas phase. JWST is the only mission in the next decade, however, that will be able to resolve those spectral features for disks in the near-IR and mid-IR, as well as thermal emission across a large fraction of known disks (up to 50%), though most of the resolved imaging will be of cold belts, rather than any warm components that may be present. To resolve warm belt components, a mid-IR facility larger than JWST or an interferometer in space would be required.

Satellites in the mid- to far-IR will be able to measure spectra and detect atomic and molecular species in the gas phase. These single dish facilities are essential to map out signatures of long period planets on their debris disks, probe dust grain properties over a statistically significant number of disks, and reach the sensitivities needed to detect true solar system analogues in the debris disk population. They will also have enough sensitivity to detect cold, small disks around low-mass stars.

The ability of interferometers to conduct blind surveys for disks is very limited due to sensitivity and the need to tailor configurations for disk properties. While we can make a decent statistical distribution of disk mean radii, the width of individual disks is likely very tuned to the planetary architecture of the system. For known disks, mm and cm interferometers like ALMA and ngVLA will provide the high resolution, high sensitivity mapping that will image known dust emission in exquisite detail. We will also have sensitivity to detect CO and Cl(ALMA) emission, and potentially OH or HI in

the disks, which would likely be sourced by photodissociation of H₂O outgassing from the planetesimals. Both these gaseous species will be detectable to ngVLA and SKA. The next generation of optical/near-IR ELTs will add significantly to our ability to image more disks in scattered light via extreme AO, detecting asymmetries in disks, while polarization data will provide a measure of dust grain porosity and thereby constrain composition.

Our ability to detect variability due to terrestrial planet formation will likely be limited for the near future to a fraction of the known young disks. Frequent monitoring of a small number of disks with JWST, or with upgraded SOFIA instrumentation may be possible. From the ground, instruments like MATISSE on VLTi could frequently visit high-priority targets, potentially several times a year. Canada's access to such instruments will be limited. LSST's continuous monitoring will no doubt detect more systems like Tabby's star, with continuous occultations of the star due to intermediary planetesimals, including clustered groups of planetesimals, such as analogues to the Trojans in our own Solar system.

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1 Introduction

Contrary to being the final tenuous stage of protoplanetary disks, debris disks (also known as “second generation disks”) arise from the collisional evolution of large solid bodies created during planet formation processes. Unlike a protoplanetary disk, which can contain dust before forming planetesimals (e.g., at the earliest stages), *a debris disk cannot exist without large planetesimal bodies to provide the dust that is observed via scattered light or thermal emission*. Observations of debris disks tell us about the scale of the underlying planetesimal belts, reveal the possible locations and masses of unseen planets, and provide a probe of the composition and dynamics of the material present. Gas emission, particularly CO, CI and OI, has been detected in debris disks, albeit in much smaller amounts than we expect for protoplanetary disks; in most cases, this gas is also generated by the collisions of planetesimals and the sublimation of volatiles, though at ages of 10s of Myr, it is possible the gas could be a remnant of the protoplanetary disk. Therefore, a practical definition of debris disks is a collisionally evolving ensemble of planetesimals and dust in a gas-poor environment. Debris disks can range in age from a few Myr to Gyrs. As such they provide, for many systems, a unique window into planetary system architecture, since the dust emission is excluded from regions of giant planets (see Figure 1). For systems of intermediate ages of a few 100 Myr, *debris disks may be the only way to probe active terrestrial planet formation which is thought to persist well beyond the lifetime of a protoplanetary disk*. Even future instruments that will probe the terrestrial regions of protoplanetary disks will capture only the conditions and earliest phases of planetary assembly there, if the final assembly of terrestrial planets occurs after gas dispersal.

The sensitive infrared surveys made possible with modern space telescopes (Herschel, WISE and Spitzer) have identified thousands of debris disk systems, but only a few hundred have a reasonably well-characterized spectral energy distributions (SEDs), and even fewer have resolved imaging at any wavelength. Most debris disks were detected via an excess of flux density above the stellar photosphere at infrared - submillimetre wavelengths, and most early resolved images were obtained via scattered light at near-IR or optical wavelengths, utilizing a coronagraph to block the stellar emission. Detecting and resolving disks at multiple wavelengths is important to their study (see Figure 2a). Debris disks are a component of planetary systems, and systems where their architecture can be resolved often show evidence of radially distributed components, with warm dust analogues to our Solar System’s asteroid belt or zodiacal light and cold dust analogues to the Edgeworth-Kuiper Belt (E-KB). A significant number of systems also show evidence of very hot dust (1000 K) very close to the parent star, detected through optical and near-IR interferometry, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Dust grains will most efficiently emit light at wavelengths close to the grain’s size. Therefore, observations of disks over different wavelengths can effectively probe the size distribution of dust grains. When multiple dust components are detected, there is reason to suspect that planets are present where the debris is absent. In a few very well known disk systems, radial and azimuthal features led to the detection of planetary companions (e.g., beta Pic by Heap et al. 2000 and Fomalhaut by Kalas et al. 2005), although the nature of Fomalhaut b is debated

Figure 1: Schematic of debris disk components defined by planetary location, in a similar configuration to the Solar System. Terrestrial planets coincide with zodiacal dust; warm planetesimal belt lies inside the orbits of giant planets and the cold E-KB lies beyond the outermost planets. Many disks also have a halo, typically detected in scattered light, but also seen for several disks in thermal emission in the infrared. The halo is populated with grains on hyperbolic orbits which have been removed from the system by radiation or stellar winds (from Holland et al., 2019, , used with permission).

Figure 2: One of the best studied debris disks, Fomalhaut, shows similar morphology at a wide range of wavelengths, from a) the optical with HST (Kalas et al., 2005), through b) the far-infrared with Herschel (Acke et al., 2012) and c) the millimetre with ALMA (MacGregor et al., 2017). Close inspection reveals key differences, such as the pericentre glow in the far-infrared, induced by the closer proximity to the star, and the opposite apocentre glow in the mm, produced by the slower orbital velocities at apocentre that concentrates dust particles at that position. The obvious offset of the star Fomalhaut from the geometrical centre of its disk emission was taken as early evidence for the presence of an extrasolar planet in the system. The currently known companion Fom b is indicated by the white circle in panel b, but there is debate regarding its nature and it is not the source of the disk/star offset.

in the literature (e.g., Lawler et al., 2015). Many more systems show features that could arise due to gravitational perturbations from planets, such as narrow rings and brightness asymmetries (e.g., MacGregor et al., 2017; Lee & Chiang, 2016; Wyatt et al., 1999).

Observations in the mid- and far-IR also do not trace the underlying population of planetesimals, probing instead small dust grains ($10 - 100 \mu\text{m}$) that are subject to radial migration induced by radiation forces (Burns et al., 1979). Observations at longer wavelengths are therefore more attractive in that the emitting grains are large enough to be co-located with the planetesimals. The advent of interferometers operating in the submm/mm (e.g., ALMA), means that high resolution imaging in thermal emission is now possible.

Recent observations of debris disks fall into two main categories: (a) placing disks (and, by implication, our Solar System) into context via statistical samples, and (b) the architecture and properties of individual systems, probed specifically by high angular resolution imaging and/or spectroscopy. Increasing numbers of detected exoplanets coupled with the surveys of the last decade have enabled some comparisons of systems containing both exoplanets and debris disks as well.

2 The Current Picture

2.1 The Solar System in Context

Debris disk science has always benefited from the parallels between observed debris disks and the structure of our Solar System, which contains hot dust near the Sun, zodiacal dust from disintegration of Jupiter family comets, a warm asteroid belt and a cold, albeit relatively collisionless, E-KB, as depicted in Figure 1. A halo is not observable in our own solar system, as the most diffuse component. The last decade has seen an improved understanding of

the demographics of debris disks, through large and relatively deep surveys of nearby stars with Spitzer, Herschel and the JCMT (the latter two of which had significant Canadian leadership, see Matthews et al. 2014 for a review). Most disks detected in these surveys were cold components located at distances from their stars comparable to the E-KB (Sibthorpe et al., 2018).

Even the deepest of the existing surveys have not succeeded in reaching the fractional luminosity of the Solar System’s E-KB (10^{-7} , Vitense et al. (2012)). The detection rates for debris disks varied by spectral type, with A-type stars around 30% (Thureau et al., 2014), and a rate of only 15% for FGK “Solar-type” (Sibthorpe et al., 2018). The faintest disks detected had fractional luminosities of just a few $\times 10^{-6}$, still an order of magnitude brighter than the E-KB. These detection rates suggest that debris disks are at least as common as planetary systems (Winn & Fabrycky, 2015), and may be ubiquitous, if Solar System type debris disks are the norm. As summarized in Hughes et al. (2018), rates of detection for hot components of exozodiacal light can be quite high, although the thresholds of our current detections are well in excess (1000 \times) that of our Solar System’s zodiacal light. Correlations have been noted between cold dust disks and hot dust (asteroid belt analogues), with no clear explanation of what is feeding hot dust components.

What the existing thresholds imply is that the disks currently being detected are scaled up versions (in size and mass) of the Solar System’s debris disk components. It is not yet possible from the available data to know whether a more quiescent population of Solar System analogues will be revealed by the next generation of more sensitive instruments.

2.2 High resolution imaging of individual systems

Prior to the current generation of AO imagers and ALMA, a few hundred disks had been imaged at any wavelength. Many of these disks were resolved with single dish facilities in the infrared/submillimetre. Such observations typically resolved the outer extent of the cold disk component, but could not resolve the inner edge of the disk. Warm and hot dust components are constrained in radii due to their temperatures, and are not typically resolved, even with current instrumentation. While much was deduced about the distribution of temperature components and cold and warm belts via these observations, there were always degeneracies in the modeling that could only be dispelled by resolving the disks.

High resolution imaging of debris disks was once restricted to scattered light imaging with HST. In the last decade, however, ground-based extreme AO systems have provided a means of decreasing the inner working angle and detecting disks emission on scales $< 1''$. This translates into an ability to see disks with radii of 50 au at distances of 100 pc, where many young associations can be targeted (e.g., Sco-Cen, 5 Myr old). Instruments such as the Gemini Planet Imager (GPI) on Gemini and SPHERE on the VLT have provided a wealth of debris disk images, revealing asymmetries and substructure, with well detected inner and outer radii. For example, HD 106906, which also has a detected companion, shows an asymmetric distribution in scattered light. The distribution differs on small scales (10s of au, seen by GPI and SPHERE) compared to large scales (100s of au, seen by HST) (Kalas et al., 2015). The planetary companion, at a 20° offset from the disk midplane, may be responsible for the dynamical evolution of the disk. In another example, HD 111520, the most asymmetric disk yet detected (Draper et al., 2016), shows different structure on either side of the disk that may be due to asymmetry in dust properties (e.g., due to a recent collision) or asymmetry in the underlying mass distribution in the disk. GPI results on several disks have been led by Canadian researchers, particularly graduate students (Millar-Blanchaer et al. (2016) [HD 157587], Draper et al. (2016) [HD 111520], and Crotts et al. 2019, in preparation [HD 106906]).

It is now possible to discriminate between grain properties and mass distribution as the source of asymmetries in scattered light. ALMA has provided an exciting new window into the distribution of emission from the larger grains. These larger grains dominate the mass budget and closely trace the planetesimal belts, which are the origin of all the dust emission. More than a dozen debris disks have been imaged in fine detail with ALMA, revealing thin rings, multiple ring systems, and broad rings. The first ALMA image of the Fomalhaut debris disk constrained the millimetre emission to a very thin ring, potentially constrained by planets (Boley et al., 2012). Although for protoplanetary disks there is no systematic correlation yet seen between the rings and gaps and the most significant snowlines (e.g., CO; van der Marel et al., 2019), resolved imaging of debris disk emission at millimetre observations

with ALMA have found a correlation between ring radial position and stellar temperature, i.e., a relation potentially related to snowlines (Matrà et al., 2018).

2.3 The Exoplanet Connection

There remain only a handful of systems in which both a debris disk and an exoplanet have been directly imaged. Unlike most exoplanet detection techniques, direct imaging detects long-period planets, which are on orbits more likely to interact with cold debris disk components than those detected by RV or transit techniques. Targeted surveys with Herschel and Spitzer derived detection rates for disks around planet-hosting stars of 20 – 30% (e.g., Marshall et al., 2014; Matthews et al., 2014). A trend has been noted between low-mass (i.e., $< 1M_{Jup}$) planets and the detection of cool dust components (Wyatt et al., 2012; Marshall et al., 2014); however, the trend does not persist in a statistically rigorous analysis (Moro-Martín et al., 2015). On the other hand, Herschel established that, in known planet-hosting systems, disks are detected at a higher rate and brightness in systems without planets exceeding Jupiter’s mass (Matthews et al., 2014).

One clear source of bias is that long-period planets are best detected via direct imaging, and current facilities can only effectively target young (< 100 Myr) systems. Constructing a bias-free comparison between exoplanets and debris disks requires an ability to sample both populations across ages and spectral types. Even though more sensitive surveys of debris disks would enable better exploration of the parameter space of young (i.e., more distant) disks and disks around low-mass stars, the existing disk-exoplanet relations can be revisited in the era of 30 m telescopes. These facilities will enable the detection of planets around older stars in reflected light. As a result, currently known disk hosts could be revealed as exoplanet hosts as well.

While the results suggest an enticing correlation between low-mass planets and debris systems, the conclusions are not statistically robust. The reason is that constructing large bias-free samples of both well-characterized disks and planets remains a challenge. New missions, such as TESS, will greatly increase the detection rate of planets around low-mass stars, but detection of their disk counterparts remains a future challenge for disk science (see Section 5.5).

3 Key Science Questions

3.1 What can we learn from gas in debris disks?

Debris disks are usually described as gas-poor, and this is true in comparison to protoplanetary disks. In the last decade, Herschel and ALMA have provided some resurgence in the interest of the gaseous component of debris disks (see review of Hughes et al., 2018). In particular ALMA has proved highly effective at detecting CO and CI around young, intermediate mass stars (e.g., Dent et al., 2014; Lieman-Sifry et al., 2016; White et al., 2016; Matrà et al., 2017a,b). The detected quantities, however, are unlikely to strongly affect the dust dynamics or planet-forming potential. Of more interest is the origin of the gas, which is not clear in young systems (where it is most typically detected). It could be either primordial or secondary (Moór et al., 2017), the latter even suggesting that CO could originate from the break-up of a narrow ring of comets, which could affect the habitability of any terrestrial planets in the system. Near-term goals include measuring the incidence of gas detections from a larger sample of systems and the detection of species other than CO, thus characterising the composition of the exocometary gas (Hughes et al., 2018). In systems in which gas emission can be mapped, there is the enticing possibility of studying the disks kinematically, as was done for Beta Pic based on CO data from ALMA (Dent et al., 2014). The quantities of gas give an estimate of the evaporation rate of comets, which has implications for planet habitability, since comets are thought to account for significant amounts of water delivery to young planets.

3.2 What can we learn about terrestrial planet assembly from variable emission?

Meng et al. (2014) opened a new window on the study of variability in debris disks when they published evidence of a rapid brightening of circumstellar infrared emission around the star ID8, more than 150 pc away. This star, one of

Figure 3: Figure from Astro2020 White Paper (Holland et al.) showing the fractional luminosities of the disks detected by the JCMT (black dots) and Herschel detected disks around Solar-type stars (Sibthorpe et al. 2018). The dashed lines show the detection curves ($3\times$ the extragalactic confusion limit) for JCMT, LMT and AtLAST, each at their optimal wavelength of observation for these objects. The E-KB is also shown, highlighting the power of a very large submillimetre single dish facility.

many now known to show rapid brightenings in flux followed by slower declines, was observed with Warm Spitzer. From the observations, the recent collision of two Earth mass bodies in the debris disk was inferred. This collision resulted in the vaporization of material, rapid sublimation back to mm grains and a slower collisional cascade of those grains to dust. The fractional luminosities of these “extreme debris disks” are very high, comparable to protoplanetary disks.

Another example of detected time variable emission is the variation of structures in the AU Mic disk on the scales of ~ 10 au (Boccaletti et al., 2015), in which models suggest that the dust is generated by a resonance or the collisions among a swarm of small bodies created in a recent giant collision. These variations are on much shorter timescales than what are expected from secular resonance effects due to planets.

The key to the detection and study of time variable emission arising from giant collisions within debris disks is the ability to monitor the emission in the infrared for an ensemble of disk hosts over an extended period of time with good cadence and consistency. The Warm Spitzer mission, which has detected most of the known extreme debris disks, is ending within the year. Continuous monitoring of disks in the mid-IR will continue to be an issue in the future, since space missions are of short duration, and mid-IR from the ground is challenging from all but the best sites.

3.3 How can we improve our global understanding of the debris disk population?

Many debris disks were first detected by measuring an excess above the stellar photospheric level at infrared through mm wavelengths. This method of identifying disks is limited by our ability to quantify the stellar emission, and we have reached the limit now. In the mid-IR and far-IR, calibrations of the photosphere set the lower limit to the level of excess that can be reliably extracted from unresolved observations. The Herschel data were aided by superior resolution that resulted in a significant fraction ($\sim 50\%$) of detected disks being marginally or well resolved.

The best current submm single dish facilities are not capable of delivering submm images of even the entire population of known debris disks. As Figure 3 shows, JCMT has hit its sensitivity limit (e.g., 50% of the known

Figure 4: (a) Wyatt (2006) figure showing the wavelength-dependent substructures induced by a planet (plus sign) within a disk. This illustrates the need for high resolution imaging across a wide range of wavelengths. (b) from Su et al. Astro2020 white paper, the importance of sufficient resolution at each wavelength is shown. Comparison of the model to 3 or 10 beams across the disk diameter shows that 10 beams are needed to be able to detect the resonance structures that would arise from due to the mass and location of an unseen perturbing planet.

targeted disks were detected by the SONS survey with SCUBA-2 Holland et al., 2017).

High sensitivity ALMA data have revealed striking disk images, but have also led to the realization that the stellar emission in the submm/mm needs to be better understood, since at these wavelengths, the stellar atmosphere models are poor and therefore can no longer reliably be used to remove stellar emission from unresolved observations, leading to ambiguous or false measurements of excess that could be interpreted as a disk (e.g. MacGregor et al., 2013; Cranmer et al., 2013). The capability to detect stellar emission at these wavelengths has led to a new avenue of stellar characterization in the submm and mm. Such work has been advanced within Canada as part of a thesis (White, 2018) and an entire program “Measuring the Emission of Stellar Atmospheres at Submillimetre/Millimetre wavelengths” (MESAS). This program utilizes a suite of facilities, including JCMT, GBT, VLA, NOEMA, and ALMA, to quantify emission from some key nearby stars, primarily Sirius A (White et al., 2018, 2019).

We note that the stellar emission can be studied in parallel with debris disk studies in cases when the disk emission is resolved from the star, eliminating confusion between the two. Future facilities that have both high sensitivity and high resolution could advance both stellar atmosphere models and debris disk studies.

Detectability is only half of the requirement to properly characterize disks and fulfill the potential of disks to reveal unseen, long period planets. High resolution imaging *at multiple wavelengths* is the key factor to identifying signatures in debris disk emission well enough to discern the presence of planets unambiguously. Therefore, we need high resolution imaging from infrared through centimetre wavelengths. Figure 4 shows the expected thermal emission as a function of wavelength for a putative planet in a disk seen face-on. It also demonstrates the need to achieve 10 resolution elements across disks to adequately characterize the radial structure and azimuthal substructure.

We note as well that detection in the submillimetre is not sufficient to fully characterize debris disks. Measurements in the infrared will remain essential to characterize the disk temperature and detect warmer components and in the mm/cm will be required to understand the size distribution and characterize the host stars across this entire wavelength range. Thus, the future detection and characterization of disks will become a high-resolution, potentially high-contrast imaging problem in the infrared. This has long been the case in scattered light imaging of disks in the optical and near-infrared, but it is now essential to approach their study at longer wavelengths with the same mindset.

3.4 What are the properties of the dust grains?

As shown in Figure 2 above, the appearance of a debris disk can vary with wavelength. Due to the collisionally-dominated origins of many of the most studied debris disks, a wide range of particle sizes is present in debris belts, with a typical power-law size distribution, usually measured via the submm/mm slope of the SED (e.g., Kennedy & Wyatt, 2014). Multi-wavelength imaging of debris disks can directly probe the particle size distribution (i.e., for signs of dynamical mixing), and further provide stringent constraints on the unseen planets and dust dynamics.

The dust composition is a relatively unstudied aspect of disks. For the few systems for which we have detailed spectra, comparisons with the Solar System can be drawn. The most significant contributing mission was Spitzer, with which the Infrared Spectrograph (IRS) was used to observe several hundred disk systems (Chen et al., 2014). Spitzer's IRS observations revealed, through unresolved spectroscopy, silicate emission toward more than 100 debris disks, with several dozen showing very prominent emission at 10 and 20 μm (Mittal et al., 2015). In addition to silicate features, water ice features should be detectable toward debris disks, revealing the amount of water present in these systems, many of which may be undergoing active collisional evolution. Lisse et al. (2009) report the detection of obsidian and tektites in the debris disk HD 172555. Since these glassy silicas form at high temperatures and pressure, their presence suggests that the system experienced a recent high velocity collision in the disk.

Sensitive infrared spectroscopy is required to enable the first statistically significant searches for solid state features in scattered light and thermal emission produced by ices and detailed characterizations of the composition, crystallinity, and grain sizes.

3.5 What is the nature of disks around Low-luminosity, Low-mass Stars?

There is a known high incidence of terrestrial planets around low-mass stars (Ballard & Johnson, 2016). The detection of debris around M stars, despite their prevalence in the galaxy and the number of known extrasolar planets around them, has proven more elusive (Lestrade et al., 2009). Even though radiation pressure is ineffective at removing grains from around M-type stars, stellar winds fill this role very well. This, coupled with the relatively old ages of nearby M-type stars may also mean that the disks have dissipated, or like the Solar System, what remains is collisionally inert.

The low number of disks detected to date around M-type stars suggests that, where they are present, they are characterized by small sizes and cold temperatures. The current limitations on sensitivity and relatively high confusion of existing single dish facilities in the submm adversely affect M-type stars more acutely, restricting much of their study to stars which are members of known young associations.

4 Facility Recommendations

The key questions above highlight the importance of high resolution and high sensitivity observations for the detection and resolution of debris disk studies in order to move the field forward. The stipulation of needing sufficient resolving power to detect substructures due to planets drives our recommendations to relatively large missions and facilities.

The most fundamental progress on thermal imaging of disks at the most scientifically rich wavelengths requires large single dish capabilities in the mid-infrared, the far-infrared and the submillimetre/millimetre.

One strong concept in the submm is the Atacama Large Aperture Submillimetre Telescope (AtLAST), which will be able to detect statistically significant numbers of new disks (1000s rather than 100s), including those around M-stars, to a fractional luminosity level at or below that of the Kuiper belt. Such a telescope would have 2'' resolution at 350 μm , meaning that *belts of comparable scale to the E-KB would be resolvable to a distance of 30-40 pc*. AtLAST would be a particularly compatible facility with ALMA, which is not an optimal facility for imaging of nearby debris disks (i.e., those within 20 pc) since even in its lowest resolution configuration, mosaicked mapping is required and the larger scale emission can be filtered out, while the ACA on its own is far too insensitive to image low-surface brightness disks. A facility like AtLAST would also have access to the molecular spectra from these 1000s of detected disks.

Emission from the cold dust components of debris disks peaks in the far-infrared. While there is a near-term potential mission, SPICA, at this wavelength, its 2.5 m mirror limits debris disk imaging to only the nearest disks and its sensitivity would be hindered by confusion with the extragalactic background, which was already an issue for Herschel observations at these wavelengths. The far-IR facility that best meets our requirements is the Origins Space Telescope. At 9m in diameter, the full scope mission would provide images at 100 μm imaging at the 2''

scale, comparable to AtLAST. The baseline mission's size of 5m would likely halve the number of disks that could be well resolved.

In the mid-infrared, SPICA also has some capability, particularly with respect to spectroscopy, which will be excellent for the detection of solid state features and detection of atomic and molecular species in the gas phase. JWST is the only mission, however, that will be able to resolve those spectral features for disks in the near-IR and mid-IR, as well as thermal emission across a large fraction of known disks (up to 50%), though most of the resolved imaging will be of cold belts, rather than any warm components that may be present. To resolve warm belt components, a mid-IR facility larger than JWST or an interferometer in space would be required. Satellites in the mid- to far-IR will be able to measure spectra and detect atomic and molecular species in the gas phase.

These single dish facilities, on the ground and in space, are essential to map out signatures of long period planets on their debris disks, probe dust grain properties over a statistically significant number of disks, and reach the sensitivities needed to detect true solar system analogues in the debris disk population. These sensitivities will also reach sufficient depth to detect cold, small disks around low-mass stars.

The ability of interferometers to conduct blind surveys for disks is very limited due to sensitivity and the need to tailor configurations for disk properties. While we can make a decent statistical distribution of disk mean radii, the width of individual disks is likely very tuned to the planetary architecture of the system, and even though the parameter space of planets beyond Jupiter's orbit is not well characterized in extrasolar systems, there is no reason to believe it to be less diverse than the inner planetary systems sampled by Kepler.

For known disks, mm and cm interferometers like ALMA and ngVLA will provide the high resolution, high sensitivity mapping that will detect dust emission in exquisite detail. We will also have sensitivity to CO and CI (ALMA) emission, and potentially OH or HI in the disks, which would likely be sourced by photodissociation of H₂O outgassing from the planetesimals. Both these gaseous species will be detectable to ngVLA and SKA in L-band (e.g., Matthews et al. 2018).

The next generation of optical/near-IR ELTs will add significantly to our ability to image more disks in scattered light via extreme AO, which we noted in Section 2.2 was one of the key developments of the past decade. These data will continue to highlight asymmetries in disks and polarization will provide excellent means of discerning the dust grain porosity and constrain composition. For some disks, this may be the only means of doing so, since scattered light emission is a highly sensitive measure of the presence of dust, detected even from relatively rarefied disks.

Our ability to detect variability due to terrestrial planet formation will likely be limited for the near future to a fraction of the known young disks. Frequent monitoring of a small number of disks with JWST, or with upgraded SOFIA instrumentation may be possible. From the ground, instruments like MATISSE on VLTI could frequently visit high-priority targets, potentially several times a year. Canada's access to such instruments will be limited.

LSST's continuous monitoring will no doubt detect more systems like Tabby's star, with occultations of the star due to intermediary planetesimals, including clustered groups of planetesimals, such as the Trojans in our own Solar system.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

Understanding the outer solar system planetary population is a challenging observational problem. Debris disks provide a window into these outer regions of systems when high resolution imaging can be attained. In addition, past the protoplanetary disk window of a few 10s of Myr, debris disk systems provide a means of watching the final stages of terrestrial planet assembly through giant collisions in the disks. The ejecta reveal mass and speed of colliders and composition of the colliders.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

Debris disks are challenging to detect, requiring large single dish facilities to capture these faint objects with

sufficient resolution to reveal substructure in the disks. The fact that the disks do not evolve with wavelength as protoplanetary disks do means it is challenging to place ages on any not in known associations; in addition, debris disks may undergo stochastic brightening at late ages, when systems have undergone recent collisions.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Two of the major debris disk surveys of the last decade had significant Canadian leadership (Matthews was PI of Herschel DEBRIS and coordinator of JCMT SONS). The earliest work on some of the most well known disks were led by, or included, Canadians. White started the MESAS project while at UBC. Future facilities like TMT and ngVLA have significant Canadian leadership. Canada has a leadership role in the development of SAFARI on Spica, but as yet not on AtLAST (the proposed 50m submm telescope) or Origins.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

Debris disk science benefits from very strong international coordination. Within Canada, there are a small number of researchers, all of whom are strong international collaborators. The debris disk community has started having yearly invitation only meetings of 30-40 people. The first was organized in Canada in 2018.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

The most important facilities required by this program have properties (high resolution and high sensitivity) required by many other subfields of astronomy. Observations in the midIR to submillimetre represent a key wavelength range that has yet to be optimally exploited. mid-IR facilities from the ground have been limited, and JWST and Spica will make a large impact, as will TMT on Mauna Kea. In the far-IR, Origins would build significantly on Herschel's success in the far-IR, for debris disk and other studies. Finally, larger submm single dishes will likely provide the key imaging for many fields from cosmology to debris disks.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

The search for, and characterization of, planetary systems is a topic that is easily accessible to the public, so there are strong outreach opportunities in this science, especially when high resolution imaging is achieved. Students are also currently drawn to exoplanet and exo-solar system studies.

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